

Characterization of wear and friction between tool steel and aluminum alloys in sheet forming at room temperature

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ABSTRACT

This work investigates the coefficient of friction (COF) at room temperature between tool steel 1.2343 and aluminum alloys EN AW-5182, EN AW-6016 as-delivered (T4) and EN AW-6016 naturally aged (T4*) using a strip drawing tribometer. In order to simulate the contact conditions of industrial sheet metal forming processes, the surfaces of the steel pins and of the aluminum strips were maintained as-delivered, i.e., the pins were wire-cut from a hardened and ground plate and the strips were cut from electrical discharge textured (EDT) and dry-lubricated sheets. Two sliding velocities, 50 mm/s and 250 mm/s, and two nominal contact pressures, 10 N/mm² and 20 N/mm², were considered. The sliding distance on each strip was 0.5 m. Each pair of pins was utilized for testing 10 or 20 strips to study the influence of increasing the sliding distance on the COF. Before and after the tribological experiments, surface topographies of selected pins and strips were analyzed using 3D optical surface profilometry, optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) combined with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Strain hardening due to plastic surface deformation of the strips was investigated using an automated hardness tester. In general, an increasing trend of the COF was observed with increasing sliding distance. The mean COF obtained for each of the tests was in the range of 0.09–0.17; however, it was considerably higher if aluminum was transferred from the strip to the pins. Moreover, moist pin surfaces were identified to increase the COF, as the originally dry lubricant became pasty and sticky which promoted entrapment of abraded aluminum particles. Slightly higher strain hardening of alloy EN AW-5182 compared to alloy EN AW-6016 caused less flattening of the strip asperities and more severe wear of the pin surface.

1. Introduction

In recent decades, aluminum sheets of the 5000- and 6000-series have been successfully introduced into the automotive industry for producing lightweight car body components [1,2]. Sheets of the 5000-series (AlMg) are almost exclusively used for components “hidden” inside the car body, e.g., for structural parts or for inner closure panels, whereas sheets of the age-hardenable 6000-series (AlMgSi) are mainly used for visible components, e.g., for outer body panels [3]. Particularly in sheet forming processes, the tribological conditions between the steel tools and the aluminum sheets have significant influence on both tool wear and quality of the components. For example, changing only the sheet material but keeping other process parameters constant may considerably affect the entire tribological system [4]. Since the coefficient of friction (COF) is one of the key parameters for simulation

models of deep drawing processes, it must be determined under relevant tribological conditions including the local contact pressure due to the applied normal force, the surface temperature of the tool, the surface roughness of the tool and the sheet, the applied lubrication, etc. [5].

Several authors have studied the tribological conditions in stamping/deep drawing of aluminum alloy sheets at room temperature. Mohamed et al. [6] investigated the influence of different types of lubricants (oil, nylon, grease and nylon-grease combination) on the formability of 1.5-mm-thick AA-6061-T4 sheets. They found that using the nylon-grease combination instead of conventional oil reduced the friction occurring between the tools and the sheet. Therefore, the height of the cups determined at the onset of necking increased about 20 %, and the variation of its wall thickness decreased markedly. Hazra et al. [7] studied the influence of varying material properties, process parameters and friction conditions (quantity of lubricant, surface roughness and

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temperature of the tool) on the formability of AA-6111-T4 and AA-5754-O sheets using also cup drawing tests. Besides the material properties, the actual tool temperature and the quantity of the lubricant were identified to influence particularly the cold formability of AA-5754-O. Although the modest increase of the tool temperature up to 55 °C during serial production was unlikely to influence the material properties, the temperature was assumed to alter the properties of the lubricant. Groche and Nitzsche [8] also stated that increasing the tool temperature from 30 °C to 65 °C when drawing lubricated 1.5-mm-thick AA-5754 strips over tool steel 1.2379 (drawing velocity 25 mm/s and contact pressure 5 N/mm²) may considerably decrease the viscosity of the lubricant, cause breakdown of the lubricant film and thus facilitate adhesive wear. For unlubricated strips they proposed that even increasing the temperature from 15 °C to 30 °C caused adhesive wear.

Dou and Xia [9] established a numerical model for describing variable friction between the steel die and formed AA-5052 sheets. Their model utilized the COF determined for boundary lubrication conditions at different sliding velocities (approx. 30–70 mm/s) and contact pressures (approx. 0.5–2.5 N/mm²) using a pin-on-disk tribometer. The COF (approx. 0.05–0.15) was observed to decrease generally with increasing sliding velocity and contact pressure; however, this general trend was weaker at higher sliding velocity and at higher contact pressure or normal force, respectively. The experiments performed by Shafiee Sabet et al. [10] showed similar results. The COF between pins of steel 1.3505 and plates of AA-6016-T4 or AA-5182, respectively, was investigated for four nominal contact pressures (4–16 N/mm²), two sliding velocities (1 mm/s and 5 mm/s), and two plate temperatures (room temperature and 100 °C) using a pin-on-plate tribometer. For both aluminum alloys, the COF at room temperature was in the range of approx. 0.06–0.14, but the COF at 100 °C was in the range of approx. 0.09–0.17. The mean COF decreased with increasing contact pressure and sliding velocity, but it increased with increasing plate temperature. Both ploughing and flattening of the surface asperities of the aluminum plates were identified as dominant wear mechanisms. Plastic deformation at the surface became more severe, if the contact pressure or the surface temperature increased. Based on these findings, utilizing a multi-factor friction model was proposed for the finite element simulation of sheet forming processes. For deep drawing with a cross-shaped tool it was exemplarily shown that this multi-factor friction model improved the predictability of blank thinning, thickness variations and geometry of the formed component, in particular at critical radius areas.

In their comprehensive review on friction in stamping processes, Li et al. [11] stated that tool (die) sticking effects have strong influence on friction and wear of aluminum alloy sheets. The transfer of particles from the sheet to the tool and the adhesion and deformation of these particles at the tool surface, the so-called galling, is an important factor affecting the actual tribological conditions. Heinrichs and Jacobson [12] found that local defects at the surface of steel tools facilitate the initial pick-up of aluminum, but according to Schedin [13] this effect seems to be virtually independent on the material combination and on the lubrication. However, the overall surface roughness was found to have stronger influence on galling of aluminum and on the friction conditions, in particular for coated tools. Thus, measures for avoiding occasional surface defects are beneficial for preventing local aluminum pick-up, but smooth and well-polished surfaces are mandatory for improving both galling resistance and friction conditions. In-situ studies [14] on needle-shaped AA-6082 pins sliding against nitrogen-alloyed powder-based cold work tool steel showed that even scratches of few microns on the tool surface can initiate immediate aluminum transfer, and even small carbo-nitrides at well-polished tool surfaces may cause initial transfer on a very small scale. Westlund et al. [15] used the identical experimental setup for investigating friction conditions and material transfer between AA-6082 sliding with or without lubrication against matrix steel or powder-based steel with different surface roughness. Under lubricated conditions virtually no aluminum transfer from the pin to the plate was observed for the smooth steel surface, and

the mean COF decreased from 0.17 (initial sliding pass) to 0.12 (tenth sliding pass). As substantial aluminum transfer was observed for the rough steel surface, the mean COF decreased from 0.32 (initial sliding pass) to 0.25 (tenth sliding pass). Although the COF was found to depend on several complex mechanisms, low-friction sliding was consistently associated to smooth sliding surfaces. Hu et al. [16] described the evolution of both the COF and the area of aluminum transfer for AA-6082-T6 pins sliding against cast iron disks. Constant sliding velocity of 50 mm/s, three contact pressures of 0.6 N/mm², 1.6 N/mm², and 3.2 N/mm² and different sliding distances up to 50 m were considered in their experiments. They observed that the aluminum transfer, the COF and the wear rate depend on the sliding distance. The transfer increased gradually during the running-in state until reaching a dynamic equilibrium in the steady state. Accordingly, the COF increased from a low initial value to a higher constant value, whereas the wear rate decreased from a high initial value to a lower constant value. With increasing contact pressure the running-in state was shorter, but the wear rate and the aluminum transfer at the steady state were higher.

Besides mill finishing (MF), electrical discharge texturing (EDT) is the most common technology for surface finishing of aluminum sheets dedicated for automotive applications [3]. Surface finishing may improve the tribological conditions between the tools and the sheets and hence the forming behavior. Aspinwall and co-workers [17,18] provided a comprehensive overview about EDT processes of mill rolls which are then used for producing sheets with EDT surfaces. Hartfield-Wunsch et al. [19] showed that EDT sheets are basically rougher than MF sheets, but the COF is more isotropic. They performed draw bead tests on different commercial aluminum sheets, which showed the highest COF in the rolling direction and the lowest COF transverse to the rolling direction. That was confirmed by Masters et al. [20], who investigated the COF for AA-5754, AA-6111 and AA-6451 strips sliding against a pair of nodular ductile iron dies. They considered different combinations of normal force, sliding velocity, lubrication, surface finish and pre-strain of the strips. Increasing the pre-strain (i.e., the amount of plastic deformation) increased the surface roughness and thus the COF of the MF strips, whereas the surface roughness and thus the COF of the EDT strips were unaffected. For the MF strips the anisotropy of the COF was independent on both the amount and the direction of pre-strain. Liewald et al. [21] studied the friction behavior of AA-5182 sheets with MF and EDT surfaces sliding against tool steel 1.2379 using a strip drawing tribometer. They considered typical conditions occurring in deep drawing processes: a strip drawing velocity of 100 mm/s, contact pressures of 5 N/mm², 10 N/mm², and 20 N/mm², as well as different angles between the sliding direction and the rolling direction. They identified the angle to influence both lubrication transport and flattening of surface asperities and thus the COF, which was in the range of approx. 0.04–0.14. However, this directional dependence decreased with increasing normal force, i.e., with increasing contact pressure. Liu et al. [22] performed identical strip drawing experiments for investigating the influence of the rolling direction on the friction behavior of AA-6016-T4 sheets with EDT surface. The drawing velocity was 50 mm/s, the contact pressure was 5 N/mm² and different wet lubricants were tested. Lubricants with additives reduced the friction compared to lubricants without additives. If lubrication was sufficient (1 g/m²) the COF was in the range of approx. 0.05–0.14; however, the COF was dependent on the angle between the drawing direction and the rolling direction of the sheet. The highest COF occurred in rolling direction, the lowest COF occurred at the angle of 30° and adhesion was observed at the angle of 45° to the rolling direction.

Ju et al. [23] evaluated the influence of different wet and dry lubricants on the friction behavior of 1.5-mm-thick AA-5182-O sheets with MF and EDT surfaces using cup drawing tests. The drawing velocity was 40 mm/s. Dry lubricants were identified as more effective for reducing friction than wet lubricants, especially combined with EDT surfaces. The lowest COF determined based on numerical simulation of the cup drawing test was 0.08. Zhou et al. [24] studied the influence of

Table 1
Chemical composition of the materials according to the supplier’s specifications in wt%.

Material	Si	Mg	Mn	Fe	Cr	Cu	C	Mo	V	Zn	Ti	Al
1.2343 (X37CrMoV5-1)	1.00	–	0.40	bal.	5.30	–	0.38	1.20	0.40	–	–	–
EN AW-6016-T4	1.32	0.36	0.06	0.19	0.01	0.01	–	–	–	0.01	0.03	bal.
EN AW-6016-T4*	1.13	0.39	0.08	0.16	0.03	0.08	–	–	–	0.01	0.03	bal.
EN AW-5182	0.08	4.40	0.35	0.22	0.01	0.03	–	–	–	0.01	0.01	bal.

AA-6111-T4 with MF and EDT surfaces within a wide range of contact pressures (2–145 N/mm²), but at low sliding velocities (2.5 mm/s, 6.5 mm/s and 14.5 mm/s) using a strip drawing tribometer. They observed load-dependent friction behavior for both EDT as well as MF sheet surfaces. EDT reduced the COF only for contact pressures greater than 62 N/mm². MF caused anisotropic friction behavior: at low contact pressure the COF was lower along the rolling direction than transverse to the rolling direction, but at high contact pressure this behavior turns into the opposite. A fundamental observation regarding the pressure-dependence was described by Emmens and Bottema [25]. They stated that aluminum alloys show generally strong flattening of roughness asperities in sliding contact, which confirms the key influence of the contact pressure on the actual friction conditions. Due to this flattening effect simply increasing the blankholder force in forming of aluminum alloy sheets does not shift the condition from mixed lubrication to boundary lubrication.

The review illustrates that lubrication plays the dominant role for determining the tribological conditions in aluminum sheet forming. Sufficient lubrication is required for the achievement of stable process conditions and for the prevention of galling. Maintaining the lubrication film during the forming process is mandatory for keeping the COF within a reasonable range. In particular EDT sheet surfaces may provide isotropic friction conditions which stabilize the lubrication film. Although the influence of the contact pressure on the COF is limited for lubricated aluminum-steel contact pairs, it seems to be more significant than the influence of the sliding velocity and the tool temperature. These conclusions are based on tribological experiments taking into account comparatively short sliding distances; however, only a few studies on steel sliding against aluminum alloys consider total distances longer than 1 m [16]. Thus, lack of knowledge about the evolution of the COF with increasing sliding distance exists. Moreover, aluminum alloy sheets of the age-hardenable 6000-series are usually delivered in T4 temper (i. e., solution-treated, quenched and naturally aged) which has very good formability and mechanical joinability. Due to continuing natural aging even at room temperature the beneficial properties of the as-delivered sheets deteriorate with time. Hence, strength and hardness increase, but the ductility decreases. The effect of natural aging on the friction behavior is still an open question which needs to be addressed. Das et al. [26] studied the effect of static and dynamic ageing on the wear and friction behavior of AA-6082 pins (as-cast, solution-treated and peak-aged) oscillating against tool steel discs, but neither the contact conditions, nor the composition or the micro- and macrostructure of the alloy reflected the typical conditions in sheet metal forming.

Therefore, the present work aims to investigate the effect of long sliding distances on the COF and on the wear behavior of tool steel 1.2343 (X37CrMoV5-1) sliding against aluminum alloys EN AW-5182 and EN AW-6016. In order to consider the influence of natural aging on the COF, alloy EN AW-6016 was tested in as-delivered (T4) as well as in naturally aged (T4*) conditions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Material properties

Strips with dimensions of 1000 mm × 15 mm × *a* mm were cut from electrical discharge textured (EDT) and dry-lubricated sheets of aluminum alloys EN AW-5182 and EN AW-6016-T4 or -T4*.

Table 2
Quasi-static tensile properties of the strips.

Material	$R_{p0.2}$ (N/mm ²)	R_m (N/mm ²)	A_g (%)	n (–)
EN AW-6016-T4	122	234	22.9	0.27
EN AW-5182	130	287	21.3	0.31

Table 3
Surface roughness parameters of the strips.

Material	R_a (μm) parallel	R_a (μm) normal	S_a (μm)
EN AW-6016-T4 / T4*	0.7	0.7	0.8
EN AW-5182	0.8	0.8	0.9

were tested in as-delivered surface condition, which is intended for direct use in deep drawing without any additional lubrication. The chemical compositions of the aluminum alloys are summarized in Table 1 and the strip thickness *a* is given in Table 4.

Quasi-static tensile properties of two aluminum alloys including yield strength, $R_{p0.2}$, tensile strength, R_m , uniform strain, A_g , and strain hardening exponent for strains between 2 % and A_g , n , were determined using a Zwick/Roell Z100 uniaxial testing machine. The testing velocity was 5 mm/min. Sample dimensions according to DIN 50125, type H (total sample length $L_t = 270$ mm, initial gauge length $L_0 = 80$ mm, sample width $b = 20$ mm), were used. Table 2 contains mean values of the tensile properties, which were calculated based on testing three samples oriented in rolling direction of the sheets. $R_{p0.2}$ indicates that plastic deformation of alloy EN AW-6016-T4 starts at lower stress than plastic deformation of alloy EN AW-5182, and n indicates that strain hardening of alloy EN AW-6016-T4 is less distinctive than strain hardening of alloy EN AW-5182.

Table 3 provides basic parameters which characterize the surface roughness of the original aluminum alloy sheets or strips, respectively. The mean profile roughness, R_a , and the mean area roughness, S_a , were calculated based on multiple measurements at both sides of three different strips. Note that the measured roughness values were within

Fig. 1. Typical topography of a pin surface.

Table 4
Parameters of the strip drawing tribometer tests.

Index of test series	Aluminum alloy EN AW-	Sheet thickness a (mm)	Nominal contact pressure p (N/mm ²)	Sliding velocity v (mm/s)	Cumulative sliding distance $\sum s$ (m)
07	6016-T4	1.1	10	50	5
03	6016-T4	1.1	10	250	5
04	6016-T4	1.1	20	50	10
05	6016-T4	1.1	20	250	10
11	6016-T4*	1.0	10	50	10
10	6016-T4*	1.0	10	250	10
09	6016-T4*	1.0	20	50	10
08	6016-T4*	1.0	20	250	10
16	5182	1.5	10	50	10
13	5182	1.5	10	250	10
15	5182	1.5	20	50	10
14	5182	1.5	20	250	10

$\pm 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ of the mean values given in Table 3. For each strip R_a was determined at ten profiles parallel (i.e., in length direction of the strips) and normal (i.e., in width direction of the strips) to the sliding direction (measuring distance 4 mm, cut-off distance 0.8 mm), and S_a was determined at two areas of approx. 5 mm \times 5 mm. As the R_a values parallel and normal to the sliding direction did not show any significant difference, the surface topography of the strips was considered as de facto isotropic.

Pins of tool steel 1.2343 (X37CrMoV5-1) with block dimensions of 10 mm \times 10 mm \times 20 mm were used. After wire-cutting radii of 1.5 mm were milled at the front end and the rear end of the blocks. The steel pins were produced from a hardened and ground plate with dimensions of 240 mm \times 80 mm \times 22 mm. Semi-finished plates of this steel grade, which are available in different dimensions, are typically utilized for manufacturing deep drawing tools. As these plates have specified hardness and surface roughness, their plain surfaces can already be used in as-delivered condition without any additional machining (e.g., for plain blankholder surfaces). Moreover, the manufactured tools are distortion- and crack-free, since hardening is not required after machining (e.g., high-speed cutting) of the tool engravings. Fig. 1 illustrates the topography of a typical pin surface. The roughness R_a in sliding direction was 0.8 μm and the hardness was 52–54 HRC. Due to unidirectional grinding the topography was distinctly isotropic and the

grinding marks were almost parallel. The sliding direction in the experiments was perpendicular to the grinding marks. Before testing the pins were put for 5 min into an ethanol bath placed in an ultrasonic cleaner.

2.2. Testing parameters

Nominal contact pressures, p , of 10 N/mm² and 20 N/mm² and sliding velocities, v , of 50 mm/s and 250 mm/s were investigated. These values represent typical process conditions in deep drawing of aluminum sheets. In particular, the comparatively high velocity of $v = 250 \text{ mm/s}$ accounts for the trend towards maximising the stamping velocity for increasing the process output. At each strip the sliding distance was 0.5 m. The dimensions of the nominal contact area between the pins and the strip, A , were 10 mm \times 7 mm. To investigate the evolution of the COF for cumulative sliding distances up to 5 m or 10 m, each pair of pins was used for testing 10 or 20 strips, respectively. Table 4 contains the parameters of the tribometer tests.

2.3. Tribometer

Adapting the blankholder force and thus the contact pressure is the primary measure for controlling the metal flow in deep drawing. In order to obtain reliable COF values for the contact surface between blank and blankholder, the design of the test must be suitable for simulating the actual tribological conditions. Based on the fundamental categorisation of tribological tests given by Bay et al. [27], Trzepieciniski and Lemu [28] proposed strip drawing tests with or without tangential compression for studying lubrication and friction between the blank and the flat blankholder. In the present work a similar testing principle was utilized; however, instead of drawing the strip through a pair of fixed flat dies, two pins were simultaneously drawn along the fixed strip. This strip drawing tribometer was successfully used in previous studies [29–32] to investigate the tribological conditions in press hardening of Al-Si-coated boron steel.

Fig. 2(a) and (b) illustrates the working principle and the main components of this tribometer. The strip was hydraulically clamped at both ends and the pretension force, F_p , was applied at one end to prevent bending of the strip during the tests. Since F_p was comparatively low in each of the tests (i.e., $F_p < 100 \text{ N}$), any considerable influence of pretension on the friction conditions can be excluded. The pins, Fig. 2 (c),

Fig. 2. (a) Working principle and (b) main components of the strip drawing tribometer, (c) steel pins, (d) pinholders carrying the pins, (e) aligning the pinholders before testing, (f) dummy strip with pressure-sensitive film for adjusting the contact area.

Fig. 3. Measured normal and friction forces vs. testing time (left column), and calculated coefficient of friction vs. sliding distance (right column) for EN AW-6016-T4* at the sliding velocity of 50 mm/s and at nominal contact pressures of (a) 20 N/mm² and (b) 10 N/mm².

were fixed with pinholders, Fig. 2 (d), which were mounted to the tribometer. A pneumatic bellow which was connected to the movable pinholder applied the normal force against the strip. After achieving the required normal force, $F_N = pA$, the screw-driven pinholder unit moved along the strip, so that the pins were drawn along the strip surface. The total tension force, F_T , was measured during each of the tests. Fig. 2 (e) shows the alignment of the pinholders before testing. Exact alignment was achieved by utilizing an adhesive pressure-sensitive film, which was stuck to both sides of a dummy strip. When the pins were loaded against this dummy strip, the pressure-sensitive film changed its color at the contact area from white to red. The initial positions of the pins were iteratively adjusted until the red print and thus the contact area between the pins and the dummy strip was perfectly rectangular (10 mm × 7 mm), as shown in Fig. 2 (f). After aligning the pins the dummy strip was removed, and the strip designated for friction testing was clamped at each end by the clamping units of the tribometer.

2.4. Data evaluation

In the tribometer tests the acquisition rate for both the normal force and the tension forces was 100 Hz. For each of the acquired data sets, $i = 1 \dots n$, the COF, μ_i , was calculated as:

$$\mu_i = \frac{F_{T,i} - F_{P,i}}{2F_{N,i}} \quad (1)$$

As schematically illustrated in Fig. 2 (a), F_T is the total tension force of the pins, F_P is the pretension force of the strip, and F_N is the normal force applied to the pins. Note that all of these three forces varied with sliding time, t , or sliding distance, s , respectively. The difference $F_T - F_P$ represents the friction force F_R . For each of the tests the mean COF, $\bar{\mu}$, was calculated within the interval of $s = 0$ and $s = 500$ mm:

$$\bar{\mu} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1(0)}^{n(500)} \mu_i \quad (2)$$

Before and after the tribological tests the surface topographies of selected pins and strips were measured using a Wyko 1100 N T 3D optical surface profiler as well as a Keyence VHX-6000 digital microscope. Material transfer on the surface of the pins was investigated using a TESCAN MIRA3 scanning electron microscope (SEM) coupled with an EDAX AMETEK Octane Super detector of 60 mm² for energy-dispersive

X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). An acceleration voltage of 10–20 kV and spot sizes of 5–50 nm were used for backscattered electron (BSE) and secondary electron (SE) imaging, as well as for the EDS measurements. Hardness maps at selected areas of the strip surface were captured using an automated EMCO-TEST DuraScan G5 hardness tester. The testing method was HV0.2, the distance between the imprints in both x- and y-direction was 0.25 mm, and for each imprint the hold time of the load was 5 s. Each hardness map was based on 57 × 44 imprints. The MATLAB software was used for post-processing the acquired data.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Coefficient of friction

The left column of Fig. 3 shows typical curves of the normal force, F_N , and of the friction force, F_R , measured at the sliding velocity of 50 mm/s and at nominal contact pressures of (a) 20 N/mm² and (b) 10 N/mm² for aluminum alloy EN AW-6016-T4*. The right column of Fig. 3 illustrates the curves of the COF, μ , which were calculated using Eq. (1). Note that only the data within the grey-marked range between $t = 0$ (pin movement starts) and $t = 5$ s (pin movement stops) were used to calculate μ between $s = 0$ and $s = 500$ mm. For $t < 0$ the pins were loaded against the strip, and for $t > 5$ s the pins are released from the strip. The oscillations of F_N result from the pneumatic valve, which periodically opens and closes to control the contact force according to the predefined value.

The friction curves show a general trend, because with increasing test number μ apparently tends to increase. While the dark blue curves in Fig. 3 (a) and (b) illustrate that μ is in the range of approx. 0.08–0.11 for Test 1, the dark red curves indicate that μ is about 50 % (a) or even 100 % (b) higher for Test 20. The moderate increase of μ is mainly related to the changing topography of the pin surfaces due to continuous scratching, as the same pins were used for the entire test series. Although the aluminum strips are significantly softer than the steel pins, scratching results from the interaction of the pin surface with the thin but hard aluminum oxide layer on the strip surfaces. However, besides this plastic deformation additional aluminum transfer from the strip to the pins (galling) was responsible for the increase of μ . This phenomenon overshadows the general trend which shows that increasing the nominal contact pressure from 10 N/mm² to 20 N/mm² tends to decrease the COF.

Taking a closer look at the curves of F_R and μ shown in Fig. 3 (a) for

Fig. 4. Measured normal and friction forces vs. testing time (left column), and calculated coefficient of friction vs. sliding distance (right column) for EN AW-6016-T4* at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s and at nominal contact pressures of (a) 20 N/mm², (b) 10 N/mm² and (c) 5 N/mm².

Test 1 reveals a sharp peak when the pin movement starts at $t \approx 0$ or $s \approx 0$, respectively. This peak indicates the transition from high sticking friction (static contact) to low sliding friction (dynamic contact) when the asperities of the pins separated from the asperities of the strip. As most of the asperities at the pin surface were flattened during Test 1, such peaks were not observed for subsequent Tests 2–20. Similar peaks were observed at Tests 1 of the other test series; however, due to the limited acquisition rate of the force sensor their detection was not always possible, especially not at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s. This is confirmed in Fig. 4, which also shows curves of the measured forces, F_N and F_R (left column), and of the calculated COF, μ (right column), at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s. Besides the nominal contact pressures of (a) 20 N/mm² and (b) 10 N/mm², the low contact pressure of (c) 5 N/mm² was investigated to confirm the expected pressure dependency of the COF. The transition from sticking friction to sliding friction is solely

visible in Fig. 4 (a), but it is not present in Fig. 4 (b) and (c). Note that only the data within the narrow grey-marked range between $t = 0$ (pin movement starts) and $t = 2$ s (pin movement stops) were used for calculating μ between $s = 0$ and $s = 500$ mm. For $t < 0$ the pins were loaded against the strip, and for $t > 2$ s the pins are released from the strip.

Comparing the diagrams in the left column of Fig. 4 reveals a distinctive dependency of the COF on the contact pressure; μ generally tends to increase if p decreases. At first sight no considerable difference between the curves shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b) exists. However, the detailed comparison of the initial tests of the test series, i.e. Tests 1–5, shows that μ is higher at the nominal contact pressure of 10 N/mm² than at 20 N/mm². For the final tests of the test series μ was in the range of approx. 0.13–0.15 for both pressures applied. Thus, the pressure dependence of the COF only existed for the initial tests. An entirely

Fig. 5. Mean coefficient of friction vs. cumulative sliding distance for aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4, (b) EN AW-6016-T4* and (c) EN AW-5182 at different sliding velocities and contact pressures.

Fig. 6. (a) Moist pin surfaces with sticky lubricant paste and adhering aluminum particles (b) pin surfaces with grooves containing adhered aluminum next to the side edges, and (c) severely scratched pin surfaces. The images were captured after Test 20, i.e. at the cumulative sliding distance of 10 m. The dimensions of the shown pin surfaces are 10 mm \times 7 mm.

different behavior was observed at the comparatively low nominal contact pressure of 5 N/mm². Fig. 4 (c) shows that μ almost doubled to approx. 0.25–0.30 at the final tests of the test series. Nevertheless, the basic trend is identical to the other test series; μ tends to increase with increasing test number, although the range of the values between Tests 1–20 is considerably wider.

Figs. 3 and 4 illustrate in detail the COF curves obtained for aluminum alloy EN AW-6016-T4*, but the COF curves obtained for aluminum alloys EN AW-6016-T4 and EN AW-5182 show similar basic trends. In order to summarize the results of the friction tests the mean COF, $\bar{\mu}$, was calculated using Eq. (2) for each of the obtained COF curves. Fig. 5 illustrates $\bar{\mu}$ depending on the cumulative sliding distance, $\sum s$. Based on the illustrated set of curves some fundamental trends can be derived.

For most of the test series, $\bar{\mu}$ is more or less in the range of 0.09–0.17 and it shows an increasing trend from Test 1 to Test 10 or 20, i.e., from $\sum s = 0.5$ m to $\sum s = 5$ m or 10 m. However, there are some obvious exceptions from this general trend which are discussed in section 3.2. Increasing the contact pressure from 10 N/mm² (orange curves) to 20 N/mm² (blue curves) tends to decrease $\bar{\mu}$ at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s, but at the sliding velocity of 50 mm/s (red and green curves) the influence of the contact pressure on the COF is not clear. Increasing the sliding velocity from 50 mm/s (green curves) to 250 mm/s (blue curves) tends to decrease $\bar{\mu}$ at the contact pressure of 20 N/mm², but at the contact pressure of 10 N/mm² (red and orange curves) the influence of the sliding velocity on the COF is also not clear. Owing to special conditions occurring during test series 05 (Fig. 5 (a), blue curve), both of these trends could not be explicitly confirmed for aluminum alloy EN AW-6016-T4 at $\sum s < 5$ m.

3.2. Wear and friction mechanisms

3.2.1. Steel pins

The blue curve (20 N/mm², 250 mm/s) shown in Fig. 5 (a) has an inverse tendency, as $\bar{\mu}$ decreases from approx. 0.16 at $\sum s = 0.5$ to approx. 0.12 at $\sum s = 10$ m. Closer examination revealed the presence of moist pin surfaces due to water condensing from the humid air on the cool surfaces of the tribometer. This phenomenon occurred because the cooling system of the tribometer was accidentally activated during the test series. When the moist surfaces of the pins touched the lubricated surface of the strip, the dry lubricant became pasty. The pasty lubricant stuck on the partially moist pin surface and entrapped abraded aluminum particles which adhered on the pin surface, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). After the pasty lubricant and thus the aluminum particles had been wiped from the pin surfaces and due to flattening of the surface asperities during the subsequent tests, $\bar{\mu}$ decreased with increasing $\sum s$ until it was comparable with the other test series. In fact, the decrease of $\bar{\mu}$ reflects that the pasty lubricant showed generally superior lubricating ability compared to the dry lubricant, but only if no abraded particles were present.

The red curve (10 N/mm², 50 mm/s) shown in Fig. 5 (b) increases steeply as $\bar{\mu}$ doubles from approx. 0.09 at $\sum s = 0.5$ to approx. 0.18 at $\sum s = 3$ m. Similar to the other curves, however, $\bar{\mu}$ tends to increase moderately between $\sum s = 3$ and 9 m, and then it even decreases to a value which is comparable with the other test series. Examination of the pin surfaces showed that the initial strong increase of $\bar{\mu}$ was caused by severe transfer of aluminum from the strip to the pin (galling). Due to insufficient pretension the strips bent slightly during this test series, which also caused the moderate decrease of F_R and μ between $s \approx 100$ and $s \approx 400$ mm, as shown in Fig. 3 (b). Thus, the pins were partially sliding over the edges of the strips, which facilitated the formation of large grooves close to the side edges of the pins, as shown in Fig. 6 (b).

Fig. 7. (a) SE and (b) BSE images of an area (1.4 mm × 3.4 mm) close to the groove at the side edge of the pin (sliding direction from bottom to top); EDS maps of (c) aluminum, (d) iron and (e) oxygen.

Fig. 8. (a) SE image of a surface area (0.8 mm × 0.5 mm) close to radius at the front end of the pin with aluminum adhesions (sliding direction from bottom to top), and EDS maps of (b) aluminum and (c) iron.

Aluminum was abraded from the edges of the strips and it adhered locally on the pins, in particular inside and in the vicinity of the grooves, as shown in the SE and BSE images and in the EDS maps of Fig. 7. The formation of grooves combined with severe local adhesion of aluminum increased $\bar{\mu}$ significantly. Subsequent “normal” scratching of the pin surface increased $\bar{\mu}$ just moderately, and mild abrasion of the pin asperities even reduced $\bar{\mu}$ to a level similar to the other tests.

The red and the green curves (10 N/mm² and 20 N/mm², 50 mm/s) shown in Fig. 5 (c) neither indicate any increasing, nor any decreasing trend of $\bar{\mu}$. This behavior was observed in particular for alloy EN AW-5182. The pin surfaces were severely scratched after the first tests, which increased the friction between the pin and the strip. Thus, $\bar{\mu}$ was initially about 20–40 % higher for alloy EN AW-5182 as for alloy EN AW-6016-T4 and -T4*. Since only moderate scratching of the pin

surfaces occurred during the subsequent tests at the sliding velocity of 50 mm/s, the anticipated increase of $\bar{\mu}$ was not explicitly observed. In contrast, $\bar{\mu}$ increased significantly at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s, as indicated by the orange and the blue curves (10 N/mm² and 20 N/mm², 250 mm/s). After the test series almost the entire pin surfaces were severely scratched, as exemplarily shown in Fig. 6 (c). The difference in the wear and friction behavior observed between the sliding velocities of 50 mm/s and 250 mm/s is assumed to originate mainly from the positive strain rate sensitivity of alloy EN AW-5182 particularly at high strain rates [33,34]. Increasing the sliding velocity increased the local strain rate and thus the flow stress of the aluminum alloy. Accordingly, the deformability of the asperities at the strip surface decreased. The less deformed asperities facilitated scratching of the pin surfaces which increased the friction between the pins and the strip. Hence, $\bar{\mu}$ tended to increase with increasing sliding distance $\sum s$ at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s.

Fig. 7 (c) and (d) confirm that almost the complete groove of the pin which is shown in Fig. 6 (b) on the left hand side was covered with aluminum. As illustrated in Fig. 7 (e) very little oxygen was detected at the groove since only a thin aluminum oxide layer formed on the surface of the adhesions. Moreover, closer examination of Fig. 7 (e) also reveals about 0.2-mm-thin lines of slightly lower oxygen concentration on the surface of the steel pin. These lines indicate local abrasion of the initial oxide layer at the asperities of the tool steel pin. Accordingly, the oxygen map allows for localizing worn areas on the pin surface. Besides the severe aluminum adhesion inside and close to the groove, adhesions oriented in the sliding direction were also found at the scratched area close to the radius at the front end of the pin, as shown in Fig. 8. These local adhesions accumulated with increasing number of tests; however, their influence on the COF was only moderate compared to the influence of the large groove.

Fig. 9 shows the typical wear of cleaned steel pins after sliding against strips of aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4, (b) EN AW-6016-T4* and (c) EN AW-5182 with the nominal contact pressure of 20 N/mm² and the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s. For each of the pins the cumulative sliding distance was 10 m. The wear differed significantly: for the EN AW-6016 alloy in conditions T4 and T4* wear occurred on just about 1/3 and 1/2 of the pin surface, respectively, whereas for the EN AW-5182 alloy wear occurred more or less on the entire pin surface. The different wear behavior is mainly due to the differences in the surface hardness and thus in the plastic deformability of the aluminum alloys. Sliding against both alloys obviously scratched the pin surfaces close to the radius at the front end of the pin, because when the pins were sliding along the strip their front end was mainly responsible for deforming the strip surface and thus for interacting with the hard layer of aluminum oxide. However, as the asperities of the softer EN AW-6016-T4 strip were easily flattened by the front end of the pins,

Fig. 9. Surfaces (10 mm × 7 mm) of selected steel pins after 10 m sliding against strips of aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4, (b) EN AW-6016-T4* and (c) EN AW-5182. The nominal contact pressure was 20 N/mm² and the sliding velocity was 250 mm/s. The sliding direction was from bottom to top, i.e., from the front end to the rear end of the pin.

Fig. 10. Typical topographies of strip surfaces of aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4, (b) EN AW-6016-T4* and (c) EN AW-5182 after Test 1 (upper row) and Test 20 (lower row) at the sliding velocity of 50 mm/s and at the nominal contact pressure of 20 N/mm². The sliding direction was parallel to the grooves and to the material pile-ups.

Fig. 11. Hardness maps of strip areas (10 mm × 14 mm) after Test 1 (upper row) and Test 20 (lower row), which visualize the increase of the surface hardness in the wear scars of aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4 and (b) EN AW-5182.

contact between the asperities and the rear end of the pins was reduced. Thus, scratching at the rear end of the pins did not occur, Fig. 9 (a), or it was limited, Fig. 9 (b). In contrast, as the front end of the pins caused less flattening of the harder EN AW-5182 strip, also the rear end of the pins came in contact with the asperities of the strip. Thus, the scratched zone on the pin surface had been extended toward the rear end of the pins, Fig. 9 (c).

3.2.2. Aluminum alloy strips

Fig. 10 illustrates typical topographies of aluminum alloy (a) EN AW-6016-T4, (b) EN AW-6016-T4*, and (c) EN AW-5182 strips with and without plastic deformation (“flattening”) of the surface during the friction tests. The nominal contact pressure between the strips and the pin was 20 N/mm² and the sliding velocity was 50 mm/s. Although each of the original sheet surfaces was electrical discharge textured, comparing Fig. 10 (a), (b) and (c) shows that the topographies were

slightly different. Despite this difference, more distinctive flattening of the asperities was observed for the comparatively soft EN AW-6016-T4 alloy than for the harder EN AW-5182 alloy, in particular after Test 1. In comparison, flattening of the asperities was generally reduced after Test 20, i.e. at the cumulative sliding distance of almost 10 m. This effect was assumed to originate from the increasing actual contact area between the pin and the strip asperities. Since the pins had not been changed during the test series, abrasive wear of the pin surfaces progressed with increasing test number, i.e., with cumulative sliding distance. This running-in increased the actual contact area between the pin surface and the strip surface as more asperities were in contact. Accordingly, local contact stresses and thus plastic deformation decreased. Surface flattening (i.e., plastic deformation) of the first and the last strip of a certain test series was more similar when the nominal contact pressure was 10 N/mm² instead of 20 N/mm². The grooves and the material pile-ups visible in Fig. 10 formed when the sharp edges of the pins ploughed the strips in the sliding direction. Thus, each of the grooves separates the flattened surface (left) from the original surface (right) of the strips. The effect of groove formation on the COF has not been studied in detail and needs further investigation.

Fig. 11 compares hardness maps captured at the center of the strips of aluminum alloys (a) EN AW-6016-T4 and (b) EN AW-5182 after Test 1 (upper row) and Test 20 (lower row). These maps visualize the local increase of the surface hardness due to plastic deformation in the wear scar for the nominal contact pressure of 20 N/mm². The area fraction of high hardness tends to decrease from Test 1 to Test 20, i.e., the plastically deformed (flattened) area fraction decreases with cumulative sliding distance. An exception to this basic trend was identified for alloy EN AW-6016-T4 at the sliding velocity of 250 mm/s, where plastic deformation of the asperities and thus surface flattening was more distinctive at Test 20 than at Test 1. This agrees well with the decrease of the COF as indicated by the blue curve in Fig. 5 (a), because friction due to asperity interlocking is limited for flat surfaces. Moreover, the hardness maps illustrate the basic difference in the strain hardening behavior of both alloys. The wear scars on the strips of alloy EN AW-6016-T4 show significantly lower hardness than the wear scars on the strips of alloy EN AW-5182.

Comparing the hardness maps of alloy EN AW-5182, Fig. 11 (b), also demonstrates that the area fraction of high plastic deformation decreases when the sliding velocity increases from 50 mm/s to 250 mm/s.

Fig. 12. Typical topographies of strip surfaces of aluminum alloy EN AW-5182 after Test 1 (upper row) and Test 20 (lower row) at sliding velocities of (a) 50 mm/s and (b) 250 mm/s.

This confirms the anticipated positive strain rate sensitivity of alloy EN AW-5182, i.e., the plastic deformability decreases with faster deformation or increasing sliding velocity, respectively. The strain rate-dependent difference in the deformation behavior of the strip surface is also illustrated in Fig. 12. Flattening of the surface asperities was obviously more pronounced at the low sliding velocity of 50 mm/s (a) than at the high sliding velocity of 250 mm/s (b).

4. Conclusions

The coefficient of friction (COF) between tool steel 1.2343 and dry-lubricated aluminum alloys EN AW-5182 and EN AW-6016 in as-delivered (T4) as well as in naturally aged (T4*) conditions with electrical discharge textured (EDT) surfaces were investigated at room temperature using a strip drawing tribometer. Two sliding velocities, 50 mm/s and 250 mm/s, two nominal contact pressures, 10 N/mm² and 20 N/mm², and cumulative sliding distances up to 10 m were considered. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- (1) For each of the aluminum alloys the COF was typically in the range of 0.09–0.17, and it tended to increase moderately with increasing sliding distance. However, this basic trend was not observed under certain conditions, e.g., if local adhesions of aluminum were present on the pin surface.
- (2) When the originally dry lubricant was in contact with water, it became pasty and stuck on the surface of the pins. Although the lubrication properties were not observed to decrease, the sticking pasty lubricant entrapped aluminum particles which partly adhered on the pin surface. These particles increased the COF significantly. Wiping the pasty lubricant from the pins decreased the COF.
- (3) Alloy EN AW-5182 showed less plastic deformation of the strip surfaces, but caused more wear of the steel pin surfaces than alloy EN AW-6016-T4 or -T4*, although the initial hardness was similar for both alloys. This was due to the more distinctive strain hardening of alloy EN AW-5182. For both alloys flattening of the strip surfaces decreased basically with cumulative sliding distance.
- (4) The initial COF was about 20 % higher for alloy EN AW-5182 than for alloy EN AW-6016-T4, which was mainly caused by

severe scratching of the pin surface already at the first test. For alloy EN AW-5182 significant increase of the COF during the subsequent tests was only observed at the high sliding velocity of 250 mm/s, but not at the low sliding velocity of 50 mm/s. Due to the positive strain rate sensitivity of alloy EN AW-5182 flattening of the asperities decreased and thus surface scratching of the pins increased at high sliding velocity.

- (5) The friction behavior and the COF determined for alloy EN AW-6016 in as-delivered (T4) and naturally aged (T4*) conditions did not differ significantly. Hence, problems when forming naturally aged sheets are mainly caused by the impaired formability due to the decreasing ductility and the simultaneously increasing yield strength. The change of the tribological conditions, however, plays only a minor role.
- (6) In order to obtain reliable results in numerical sheet forming simulations, one must consider the change of the tool surface roughness and thus the variation of the actual COF with cumulative sliding distance. Hence, based on the results of the present study the influence of the COF in deep drawing of aluminum will be investigated by considering blankholders with both virgin and worn surfaces.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors report no declarations of interest.

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References

- [1] Miller WS, Zhuang L, Bottema J, Wittebrood AJ, De Smet P, Haszler A, et al. Recent development in aluminium alloys for the automotive industry. *Mater Sci Eng A* 2000;280:37–49.
- [2] Taub A, De Moor E, Luo A, Matlock DK, Speer JG, Vaidya U. Materials for automotive lightweighting. *Annu Rev Mater Res* 2019;49:327–59.

- [3] Bloeck M. Aluminium sheet for automotive applications. In: Rowe J, editor. *Advanced materials in automotive engineering*. Woodhead Publishing Ltd; 2012. p. 85–108.
- [4] Groche P, Callies T. Tribology in sheet metal forming with regard to challenges in lightweight construction. *Adv Mater Res* 2005;6–8:93–100.
- [5] Nielsen CV, Bay N. Review of friction modeling in metal forming processes. *J Mater Process Technol* 2018;255:234–41.
- [6] Mohamed M, Farouk M, Elsayed A, Shazly M, Hegazy AA. An investigation of friction effect on formability of AA 6061-T4 sheet during cold forming condition. *AIP Conf Proc* 2017;1896:080025.
- [7] Hazra S, Williams D, Roy R, Aylmore R, Smith A. Effect of material and process variability on the formability of aluminium alloys. *J Mater Process Technol* 2011; 211:1516–26.
- [8] Groche P, Nitzsche G. Influence of temperature on the initiation of adhesive wear with respect to deep drawing of aluminum-alloys. *J Mater Process Technol* 2007; 191:314–6.
- [9] Dou S, Xia J. Analysis of sheet metal forming (stamping process): a study of the variable friction coefficient on 5052 aluminum alloy. *Metals* 2019;9:853. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met9080853>.
- [10] Shafiee Sabet A, Domitner J, Öksüz KI, Hodzic E, Torres H, Rodríguez Ripoll M, et al. Tribological investigations on aluminum alloys for the simulation of deep drawing processes. 2021. Submitted for publication.
- [11] Li G, Long X, Yang P, Liang Z. Advance on friction of stamping forming. *Int J Adv Manuf Technol* 2018;96:21–38.
- [12] Heinrichs J, Jacobson S. The influence from shape and size of tool surface defects on the occurrence of galling in cold forming of aluminium. *Wear* 2011;271: 2517–24.
- [13] Schedin E. Galling mechanisms in sheet forming operations. *Wear* 1994;179: 123–8.
- [14] Heinrichs J, Olsson M, Jacobson S. New understanding of the initiation of material transfer and transfer layer build-up in metal forming – in situ studies in the SEM. *Wear* 2012;292–293:61–73.
- [15] Westlund V, Heinrichs J, Jacobson S. On the role of material transfer in friction between metals: initial phenomena and effects of roughness and boundary lubrication in sliding between aluminium and tool steels. *Tribol Lett* 2018;66:97.
- [16] Hu Y, Zheng Y, Politis DJ, Masen MA, Cui J, Wang L. Development of an interactive friction model to predict aluminum transfer in a pin-on-disc sliding system. *Tribol Int* 2019;130:216–28.
- [17] Aspinwall DK, Wise MLH, Stout KJ, Gho THA, Zhao FL, El-Menshawey MF. Electrical discharge texturing. *Int J Mach Tools Manuf* 1992;32(1–2):183–93.
- [18] Simão J, Aspinwall DK, Wise MLH, El-Menshawey MF. Mill roll texturing using EDT. *J Mater Process Technol* 1994;45:207–14.
- [19] Hartfield-Wunsch SE, Cohen D, Sanchez LR, Brattstrom L-E. The effect of surface finish on aluminum sheet friction behavior. *SAE Int J Mater Manuf* 2011;4(1): 818–25.
- [20] Masters IG, Williams DK, Roy R. Friction behaviour in strip draw test of pre-stretched high strength automotive aluminium alloys. *Int J Mach Tools Manuf* 2013;73:17–24.
- [21] Liewald M, Wagner S, Becker D. Influence of surface topography on the tribological behaviour of aluminium alloy 5182 with EDT surface. *Tribol Lett* 2010;39:135–42.
- [22] Liu X, Liewald M, Becker D. Effects of rolling direction and lubricant on friction in sheet metal forming. *Trans AIME J Tribol* 2009;131:042101.
- [23] Ju L, Mao T, Malpica J, Altan T. Evaluation of lubricants for stamping of Al 5182-O aluminum sheet using cup drawing test. *Trans ASME J Manuf Sci Eng* 2015;137: 051010.
- [24] Zhou R, Cao J, Wang QJ, Meng F, Zimowski K, Xia ZC. Effect of EDT surface texturing on tribological behavior of aluminum sheet. *J Mater Process Technol* 2011;211:1643–9.
- [25] Emmens WC, Bottema J. Friction of aluminium in deep drawing. In: *Proc 20th IDDRG Congr*; 1998. p. 203–14.
- [26] Das S, Pelcastre L, Hardell J, Prakash B. Effect of static and dynamic ageing on wear and friction behavior of aluminum 6082 alloy. *Tribol Int* 2013;60:1–9.
- [27] Bay N, Olsson DD, Andreassen JL. Lubricant test methods for sheet metal forming. *Tribol Int* 2008;41:844–53.
- [28] Trzepieciniski T, Lemu HG. Recent developments and trends in the friction testing for conventional sheet metal forming and incremental sheet forming. *Metals* 2020; 10:47. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met10010047>.
- [29] Hernandez S, Hardell J, Prakash B. High temperature friction and wear of boron steel and tool steel in open and closed tribosystems. *Tribol Trans* 2018;61:448–58.
- [30] Deng L, Pelcastre L, Hardell J, Prakash B, Oldenburg M. Experimental evaluation of galling under press hardening conditions. *Tribol Lett* 2018;66:93.
- [31] Mozgovoy S, Hardell J, Deng L, Oldenburg M, Prakash B. Tribological behavior of tool steel under press hardening conditions using simulative tests. *Trans AIME J Tribol* 2018;140:011606.
- [32] Mozgovoy S, Alik L, Hardell J, Prakash B. Material transfer during high temperature sliding of Al-Si coated 22MnB5 steel against PVD coatings with and without aluminium. *Wear* 2019;426–427:401–11.
- [33] Kabirian F, Khan AS, Pandey A. Negative to positive strain rate sensitivity in 5xxx series aluminum alloys: experiment and constitutive modeling. *Int J Plast* 2014;55: 232–46.
- [34] Yamada H, Kami T, Mori R, Kudo T, Okada M. Strain rate dependence of material strength in AA5xxx series aluminum alloys and evaluation of their constitutive equation. *Metals* 2018;8:576. <https://doi.org/10.3390/met8080576>.